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INSTITUTIONALIZATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GOVERNMENT AND CIVIL SOCIETY IN THE CONTEXT OF MANAGEMENT DECISIONS

ІНСТИТУЦІОНАЛІЗАЦІЯ ВЗАЄМВІДНОСИН ВЛАДИ ТА ГРОМАДЯНСЬКОГО СУСПІЛЬСТВА У КОНТЕКСТІ ПРИЙНЯТТЯ УПРАВЛІНСЬКИХ РІШЕНЬ

Nataliia O. Briushkova, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor
Odessa National Academy of Food Technologies, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-5720-0623
Email: natashabrju@ukr.net

Olena V. Nikoliuk, DEcon, Professor
Odessa National Academy of Food Technologies, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-1665-0361
Email: alenavn11@gmail.com

Natalia A. Dobrianska, DEcon, Professor
Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-0826-8840
Email: semen-198@te.net.ua

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Institutional transformations that occur in parallel with changes in modern socio-political life of Ukraine significantly increase the responsibility of public administration for the results of social change, highlighting the role of the state as an important actor in developing and implementing public policy, which regulates the interests of various socio-political groups. Refusal to formalize the institutional component of public management of development, its orientation to the needs of democratization of modern public life indicate the importance of forming and implementing in real public administration practice effective democratic mechanisms for the implementation of public administration. In turn, it is necessary to use the positive world practice of ensuring the process of formation and implementation of the institutional mechanism of public administration, based on the use of intellectual potential of society as a whole, development of consensus and partnership, organization of open dialogue between government, modern political elite and civil society.

Analysis of recent research and publications

In recent years, the problem of establishing a mechanism for effective interaction between the state and civil society institutions has become quite acute in Ukraine. This issue is raised by a large number of domestic scientists, namely: M. Boychuk, V. Golub, V. Grabovsky, I. Grishova, G. Daudova, P. Gural, V. Ladychenko, N. Lipovska, A. Matiychuk,

Брюшкова Н.О., Ніколюк О.В., Добрянська Н.А.
Інституціоналізація взаємовідносин влади та громадянського суспільства у контексті прийняття управлінських рішень. Оглядова стаття.

У статті обґрунтовано напрями удосконалення інституційного механізму управління взаємовідносинами між державною владою та громадськістю. Встановлено, що залучення громадян через різні форми до формування й реалізації інституційного механізму управління взаємовідносинами між державною владою та громадськістю, процесу прийняття публічних рішень відображає нову модель такої взаємодії. Запропоновано модель використання інституційного механізму управління взаємовідносинами влади та громадянського суспільства.

Ключові слова: управління, публічне управління, управлінські рішення, інституційний механізм, взаємовідносини, громадянське суспільство

Briushkova N.O., Nikoliuk O.V., Dobrianska N.A.
Institutionalization of the relationship between government and civil society in the context of management decisions. Review article.

The article substantiates the directions of improvement of the institutional mechanism of management of relations between the state power and the public. It is established that the involvement of citizens through various forms in the formation and implementation of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public, the process of public decision-making reflects a new model of such interaction. A model of using the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and civil society is proposed.

Keywords: management, public administration, management decisions, institutional mechanism, mutual relations, civil society

N. Melnyk, M. Mesyuk, V. Nadraga, O. Tolkachov and others.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

However, even given the significant scientific developments in the formation and implementation of the management system of relations between government and the public, the issues of theoretical and methodological justification of institutional mechanisms in public administration remain poorly understood.

The aim of the article is the theoretical and methodological substantiation of the directions of improvement of the institutional mechanism of management of relations between the state power and the public.

The main part

One of the basic characteristics of public administration is its democracy, in fact, it is said that only in a democratic society will be provided appropriate conditions for the formation and development of mechanisms for the implementation of public administration. The quality of public administration directly depends on the level of balance in the political and administrative system and the implementation of those governance mechanisms that society needs. Just as modern civil society is a certain slice of society, and its development testifies to the level of its effectiveness, so public administration is a slice of politics and management, testifies to the existence of a certain balance in the system of government [1]. This understanding of the content of democratic processes in society determines the attitude to public administration, which under certain conditions of democracy and participation in such a process of institutions and subjects of civil society, has a new meaning. First of all, it should be agreed that "public administration ensures the existence of channels for reaching a consensus in resolving social problems, including overcoming crises." However, this requires effective mechanisms for managing the relationship between government and the public, able to ensure the integrity, comprehensiveness and coherence of the impact of relevant civil society institutions not only on the development and implementation of public administration, but also on the level of democratization in society.

Thus, today there is no doubt that the involvement of citizens through various forms in the formation and implementation of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public, the public decision-making process reflects a new model of such interaction. However, on the one hand, the system of public administration is a tool for influencing the dynamic processes of regulation through direct and indirect public involvement in rule-making, and on the other hand, the legal framework forms ways and opportunities to implement the institutional mechanism of public relations.

Researchers rightly draw attention to the importance of ensuring the conditions under which preparation, public discussion, or deviations shape the

life cycle for bills that regulate public participation in relevant political and managerial decisions, the relationship between citizen and state. In this case, on the one hand, the legal mechanism for implementing public policy as a process of settling political and managerial decisions and effective interaction can not function effectively due to lack of necessary procedures, and on the other - there is an urgent need for an institutional mechanism for managing relations between public authorities and the public [2].

With this in mind, the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public should be seen as an integral part of a well-organized and well-functioning, complementary system of social development management. It is the complexity of such a mechanism implies a certain division into groups. Such groups are presented in studies [3], where groups of socio-political mechanisms are identified, which, taking into account the function of ensuring policy stability and development at specific stages of transition from one state to another, regulate, regulate and determine the level of socio-economic interests. objects of social development, represent the regulations that ensure the implementation of effective socio-economic policy, the adoption of sound management decisions to ensure the activities of social development. Another group is the Institute of Public Relations (briefings, media, press conferences, public discussions), which is designed to take into account the needs and interests of different segments of the population, the settlement of private interests with regional and national" [4]. However, such a mechanism is quite imperfect, given the possibility of virtually open manipulation of consciousness and the individual, the implementation of shadow mechanisms of so-called "prior agreement", which leads to redistribution of responsibilities to civil society and resources at different levels in favor of authorities.

The group of mechanisms also includes institutions that "unite certain people around a common goal and are a reflection of the political stratification of society; unions, etc., without which to reconcile public interests, mobilize resources for the implementation of development programs (without taking into account the proclamation of their national importance, to a greater or lesser extent they pursue corporate/industry interests) is not possible" [2].

A certain imperfection of mechanisms associated with the complex socio-political situation in Ukraine, which belongs to the transit type of society, significantly emphasizes the importance not only to take this situation into account in forming an institutional mechanism for managing relations between government and the public, but also to minimize the negative consequences. "For post-totalitarian countries of public administration. It is not possible or effective to carry out such minimization only by managerial influence in conditions when the existing social consciousness is deformed and is under the destructive influence of the mass media engaged by various socio-political forces." As researchers rightly point out, "in Ukraine, when there is a

conscious reform of the market economy, socio-political and administrative systems, the mechanism and sequence of institutional changes is usually the import of institutions that have proven themselves in countries that have successfully overcome the transformation. That is, this version of institutional transformations is much more complex and actualizes the role of the state, makes it the main (performs the functions of authorizing the selection of the optimal institutional model, organizational support and implementation of the process, identification of efficiency and effectiveness, adjustment and overcoming problems), also due to imitation and fundamental trajectory change for development, leading to complex interaction of existing informal institutions within new formal institutional boundaries" [5]. There is one key shortcoming in this generally correct approach: the justification of the decisive role of the state in regulating the processes of democratic development of society is the result of reduced activity of civil society institutions and actors, but they are the leading forces that ensure the effectiveness of democratic development. The application in the practice of public administration of effective approaches of other countries to ensure the institutional development of a democratic society is important, but only at certain (usually initial) stages of this process. Functionally, the implementation of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public, have significant potential for the transformation of society and increase the effectiveness of management of its development.

Interaction between the relevant European institutions and society takes place in diversified areas [2-6]:

- The European Parliament as a certain elected representation of European citizens;
- institutionalized advisory bodies of the European Union (Economic and Social Commission and the Commission of the Regions), in accordance with their roles proclaimed in the agreements;
- formalized direct contacts with certain stakeholders.

The objectives for ensuring proper consultation for the various parties involved in the process are as follows [7-8]:

- ensure the involvement of stakeholders in a transparent consultation process, promote the accountability of the Commission;
- ensure compliance with the principle and standards for the establishment of the consultation process, which would help the Commission to streamline consultation procedures and make them sound and systematic;
- create a framework for consultation that is phased but more flexible to take into account the specific requirements of the diversity of certain interests, as well as the need to develop appropriate consultation strategies for each project proposal;
- mutual learning and exchange of positive experiences within such a Commission.

Consultation mechanisms are part of the European institutions' regulatory process, from the policy formulation stage before the Commission proposes for legislative decision-making and implementation. In turn, depending on the issues to be considered, such consultations are aimed at creating opportunities for cases for representatives of local authorities, civil society, enterprises and professional associations, various interested citizens, professionals and experts, representatives of non-EU countries.

In this context, the functioning of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public, allows the realization of national interests based not only on setting parameters, goals, taking into account the functioning of public administration, civil society and local government, but also within the intensification of government dialogue society, determine the balance of interests and political and legal regimes of interaction of each individual, society and state.

The implementation of the task of optimizing political and public administration intersects with the task of efficiency and effectiveness of public administration in the context of optimizing social, political and public administration systems using new mechanisms of cooperation between civil society and government, which would minimize the negative consequences of social and administrative reforms. In fact, it is important to use an institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public, which aims to coordinate the actions of government and the interests of civil society in the adoption and implementation of relevant public policy and public administration decisions.

However, the analysis of the development of civil society in Ukraine shows a set of problems that are relevant for both society and the state [6-9]:

- there are tendencies towards non-transparency, secrecy and bureaucratization in the activities of executive bodies and local self-government bodies instead of establishing an effective dialogue with society;
- imperfection of current legislation creates artificial barriers to the formation and operation of civil society institutions;
- mechanisms of public participation in the formation and implementation of public policy are not properly implemented;
- the tax burden does not stimulate the activities and development of civil society institutions and their support by domestic charitable organizations;
- most civil society institutions do not have access to state financial support and domestic charitable support;
- the potential of civil society institutions to provide social services to the population is not used.

Thus, we can state that not only the state, but also the institutions of civil society show their inability, unwillingness and unwillingness to participate in the processes of state formation and, above all, to take responsibility for their own actions. However, this is reflected in low civic position and awareness of one's

own importance in presenting social development priorities.

Implementation of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public in Ukraine to ensure organizational conditions for public participation in the formation and implementation of public policy at all levels and public control over the activities of executive and local governments [7]:

- conducting systematic consultations with the public in the process of making relevant decisions by executive authorities and local governments, timely publication of draft relevant acts on the relevant official websites of such bodies, the use of other mechanisms of interaction;
- work of public councils and other advisory bodies at executive bodies and local self-government bodies, establishment of mechanisms of their interaction with advisory bodies, first of all, by development of offers on introduction of necessary changes to Standard regulations of activity of local state administration and to operating regulations of bodies executive;
- creating conditions for conducting public examinations of the activities of executive bodies, local governments, public anti-corruption examinations of draft regulations and ensuring that their recommendations are taken into account;
- methodical support and increase of organizational capacity of executive bodies and local self-government bodies for realization of procedures of

involvement of the public in realization of the state, regional policy;

- e-government and e-democracy;
- development of mechanisms of social partnership between government, business and civil society institutions;
- promoting the involvement of civil society institutions in social dialogue on issues that cannot be resolved within the framework of tripartism, improving the mechanisms of participatory democracy in the field of labor relations;
- settlement of the issue of mandatory adoption by local governments of the statutes of territorial communities, which provide legal mechanisms for exercising the right of members of territorial communities to implement forms of local democracy (general meetings, public hearings, local initiatives, self-organization, etc.).

The solution of the tasks defined in the institutional mechanism of management of relations between the state power and the public provides in the course of realization of the state policy of assistance to development of a civil society by application of the complex approach. It is a question of expediency of formation and realization in practice of the complex institutional mechanism of management of mutual relations between the government and the public which allows to coordinate various directions of optimization of interaction of public authorities, local governments and institutes of civil society in public management (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Model of using the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and civil society

Source: authors' own development

Thus, today there is state support for the institutional activities of the formation of civil society, including at the local level. Based on the study, the following proposals can be formulated to improve the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public:

- legitimization and legal regulation of public councils, obtaining the appropriate status, the ability to represent the interests of the public in public authorities and local governments. It is important to involve scientists and specialists in such fields in such activities;
- ensuring transparency and openness of public authorities and local governments on the basis of publicity, which can minimize neglect of the interests and position of citizens; involvement of civil society institutions in the process of informing state bodies, in particular taking into account the results of public hearings, consultations, discussions, etc.;
- legislative and regulatory support of institutional development of civil society in order to ensure the effectiveness of the process of development, adoption and implementation of public policy and public administration decisions, consolidation of effective institutional mechanisms of public influence on state policy in the field of public interest;
- increase of effective activity of advisory and consultative, first of all, public bodies at authorities of various levels on the basis of formalization of interaction between advisory councils and state bodies;
- definition and consolidation of legal norms that would not only regulate the relations of civil society institutions of public authorities, but also the criteria for selecting the effectiveness and efficiency of a particular public institution in the implementation of the institutional mechanism for managing relations between public authorities and the public;
- formation of a system of public opinion monitoring on the effectiveness of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between state power and the public at the state, regional and local levels; ensuring timely state and political response to trends in public opinion, its consideration in the development of public administration decisions;
- ensuring publicity of the procedure of preparation and adoption of public-political and state-

administrative decisions on the basis of involvement of public institutions not only at the stages of their development, but also control over implementation in order to timely and adequately respond to problems arising from public opinion;

- openness, timeliness and comprehensive access to information on the activities and decisions of state bodies (except for information with limited access) for proper control over the adoption and implementation of socially significant public policy and public administration decisions;
- expanding the scope of publicity on the basis of expanding the space of public organizations in order to overcome negative social phenomena (corruption, etc.);
- formation of favorable conditions for the functioning of various forms of social activity, etc.

Conclusions

Thus, it can be noted that today there is a need for systematic modernization of state and public institutions in order not only to determine the strategic directions of public policy, but also to form support for reforms both among the general public and in the professional environment. In this context, having a clearly defined strategy and strengthening the program component of public policy would significantly increase the ability to involve in the development and implementation of public policy and public administration decisions.

An important area of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public is to improve public consultation. Intensification of public consultations will contribute to the formation of a consolidated position on the content and direction of public policy. Another important task is to address the issue of strengthening public-private cooperation and strengthening the institutional capacity of public policy mechanisms by updating personnel policy, in particular in the civil service (for example, through the use of a competitive mechanism of personnel rotations). In turn, the system of public administration needs to update the basic model, its reorientation to strengthen the institutional capacity of civil society in the implementation of public policy through effective interaction with public authorities and local governments. In this context, it is important to establish fruitful cooperation between them in order to coordinate actions in the public sphere.

Abstract

The article substantiates the directions of improvement of the institutional mechanism of management of relations between the state power and the public. An important area of the institutional mechanism for managing the relationship between government and the public is to improve public consultation. Intensification of public consultations will contribute to the formation of a consolidated position on the content and direction of public policy. Another important task is to address the issue of strengthening public-private cooperation and strengthening the institutional capacity of public policy mechanisms by updating personnel policy, in particular in the civil service (for example, through the use of a competitive mechanism of personnel rotations). In turn, the system of public administration needs to update the basic model, its reorientation to strengthen the institutional

capacity of civil society in the implementation of public policy through effective interaction with public authorities and local governments. In this context, it is important to establish fruitful cooperation between them in order to coordinate actions in the public sphere. Thus, it can be noted that today there is a need for systematic modernization of state and public institutions in order not only to determine the strategic directions of public policy, but also to form support for reforms both among the general public and in the professional environment. In this context, having a clearly defined strategy and strengthening the program component of public policy would significantly increase the ability to involve in the development and implementation of public policy and public administration decisions. The solution of the tasks defined in the institutional mechanism of management of relations between the state power and the public provides in the course of realization of the state policy of assistance to development of a civil society by application of the complex approach. It is a question of expediency of formation and realization in practice of the complex institutional mechanism of management of mutual relations between the government and the public which allows to coordinate various directions of optimization of interaction of public authorities, local governments and civil society institutions in the field of public administration.

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